

THE IMPORTANCE OF LITERARY TRANSLATION IN TRANSLATION STUDIES

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Abstract. Translation is the communication of the meaning of a source-language text by means of an equivalent target-language text. Today in teaching and learning process translation plays an important role. By the help of translation readers can understand the rules or the context. That's why this article describes importance of literary translation in translation studies.

Keywords: Translation, literary translation, translation of poetry, translation style.

Translation is a type of literary work that consists in re-creating a text in one language in another language. Translation is the most important form of international communication. Depending on the nature of the original and restored text, it is divided into artistic translation, scientific translation and other types. Depending on the way the original is represented, it can have the form of tafsir, translation, and commentary. Translation arose in ancient times due to the need for communication between people of different tribes. This type of spoken language, called Tilmokhlik, is still preserved today.

Over time, the requirements for translation are updated. But its creative character, the art of re-creation, does not change. The extent and progress of translation depends on the educational level of each nation and, in turn, it effectively affects the social thinking of the nation. The term "translation" refers to the process of translation from one language to another, as well as to the finished work of translation. The main feature of artistic translation comes from the artistic function of language. Language becomes an aesthetic phenomenon, a fact of art in a work of art. The language of a literary work is an element of a separate "artistic reality". In the translation, the artistic meaning of this figurative expressive language is

transferred to the figurative expressive ground of another language, the process of re-expressing the image with the image takes place. Therefore, the translator perceives the process of artistic thinking of the events in the work anew. Modern translation according to the requirements, the translator must recreate the unity of form and content of the original as a work of art, preserve the national and individual characteristics. The translator relies on the level of development of the native language, traditions and experiences of translation, takes into account the existence of various differences. The creative ability and knowledge of the translator expands his capabilities. Translation during the process, the translator always thinks in his native language, the native language serves him as a tool of analysis, a test criterion. For example, Qutb, who turned Nizami's epic "Khisrav and Shirin" ("...I cooked halwa from Nizami's child"), is a work of translation and copying instead, he says that it is a creative process, and a translator should be a skilled writer who cooks holva from a child.

The art of translation begins with reading, writing, and editing; the same skills a writer uses. A translator must be able to understand and appreciate the text in its original form, and then will use the resources of a writer: style, tone, diction, word choice, grammar, imagery, and idiom, to name just a few, to create a new version of the work that provides this experience to readers in the new language. Literary translators have sometimes been termed "double agents," serving two masters like spies who work for both sides, the original author and the reader in the target language. They must also understand the many varied contexts of the text, its time period, geography, and style and how those contexts affect translations for readers who are in different contexts. Just as a double agent will likely make compromises in his or her work, a translator must strike a balance as a text is ushered from one language into a new one. The literary environment of a certain region in different periods, especially the emergence of special schools of translation, shows that it had its established principles and traditions. Translation of literary works (novels, short stories, plays, poems, etc.) is considered a literary

pursuit in its own right. Notable in Canadian literature specifically as translators are figures such as Sheila Fischman, Robert Dickson, and Linda Gaboriau; and the Canadian Governor General's Awards annually present prizes for the best English-to-French and French-to-English literary translations. Translation is not copying; the translator's aesthetic need leaves a mark on the Translation beyond his discretion. If the writer artistically expresses his observations from life events in the language, the translator re-embodies the original text in a new language. For this, he needs to know the author's level of the reality mentioned in the work. Translation has a great influence on the development of the literature of every nation, because the history of translation is equal to the history of literature.

Literary translation consists of the translation of poetry, plays, literary books, literary texts, as well as songs, rhymes, literary articles, fiction novels, novels, short stories, poems, etc.

Style is the essential characteristic of every piece of writing, the outcome of the writer's personality and his emotions at the moment; a single paragraph can't be put together without revealing to some degree the personality of the author. Every writer has a literary style and his style is reflected in his writing. Some authors say that a translation should reflect the style of the original text while others say that a translation should possess the style of the translator.

A good translator should have a thorough knowledge of the source and target languages, be able to identify with the author of the book or poem, understand his culture and country, and employ a good method for translating literary texts.

The literary translator has to take into account the beauty of the text, its style, the lexical, grammatical and phonological features. Some of these may not be the same in the target language. For example, in the Arabic language there is no "you," which may be fundamental for a good translation. The aim of the translator is that the quality of the translation be the same as the original text without leaving out any of the content.

In general, in literary translation we translate messages, not meanings. The text must be seen as an integral and coherent piece of work. For example, if we are translating from Arabic into English or vice versa, we must take into account that the two realities are very different, their cultures have sometimes opposite views on certain matters, as well as on scientific and technological development. So the search for equivalent words is more complex.

When this is the case, the translator must find words in his own language that express almost with the same fidelity the meaning of some words of the original language, for example, those related to cultural characteristics, cooking skills or abilities of that particular culture.

Some ideas or characteristics are not even known or practised in the other culture. The practice of literary translation has changed as a matter of globalisation, texts have become more exotic, and these translations should contribute to a better and more correct understanding of the source culture of a country.

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